

Digital Literacy: The Hallmark of Contemporary Higher Education

Dankwalba, Abdullahi Isyaka

Baze University Abuja

dankwalba123@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19075132>

Abstract

The need to be digitally literate becomes not only necessary, but essential especially in higher education. This chapter discusses digital literacy as a hallmark of the contemporary higher education; the chapter also explained the chronological development of Digital Literacy (DL) from traditional literacy, visual literacy, media literacy and information literacy to now modern literacy in higher education (digital literacy) which indicates the innovation and development of literacy in education. Contemporary education, academic technology and technological disruption in education were discussed. Academic technology and digital literacy inclusion strategies in higher education were also discussed. Furthermore, the chapter explained digital literacy as a component of life skill and encouraged the stakeholders in higher education such as universities management, academia and faculty members to train students and teach digital literacy as a core course in general studies in the universities and colleges as part of inclusion strategies. Other higher education technology trends to watch out include Artificial Intelligence (AI), Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Digital Twins, the Metaverse (including digital avatars and NFT art for use in the Metaverse and other Web3-based virtual environments), Internet of Things (IoT), Blockchain, Cloud, Gamification, and Chatbots were all explained.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, Traditional Literacy, Academic Technology, Higher Education, Education Technology Trend and Inclusion Strategies.

Introduction

The term literacy is central to many academic disciplines and societies; all changes to media environment meaning that the focus shifts from print to information technology (IT). During the past two decades, traditional literacy expanded to include information, digital, science, visual, and multimedia literacies. Therefore, the current Digital Literacy (DL) term is an overarching keyword often used as a synonym for (digital) learning competency and knowledge. Säljö (2012) argues that literacy competency allows a person to engage in modern digital literacies as well as learning, it alters an individual's epistemic practices in many ways. According to Christiaan (2016) literacy in this day is not complete if a person is not capable of accessing and creating digital information. He added that digital literacy is strongly connected with e-learning and is highly relevant to contemporary education and today we find ourselves on a flipside of students who are digital immigrants as

well as digital natives. Within this shift, students born after 1980 were inherently better suited to navigating the rapid and continual development of the digital technologies. Digital Natives, or the Net Generation as they came to be known, they presumed to have had the greatest exposure to digital technologies. Oblinger (2005) described this generation of students as "...digitally literate, constantly connected to digital literacy. Literacy now is the ability to identify, understand, interpret, compute, and create communication in an increasingly digital, text-mediated, information-rich and fast-changing world. Literacy involves a continuum of learning in enabling individuals to achieve their goals, to develop their knowledge and potential, and to participate fully in their community and wider society (UNESCO, 2021).

Higher education faces a digital literacy imperative, where new digital technologies include advantages, and limitations, requiring

new literacies. National Center for Educational Statistics (NCES, 2000) defines higher education as: an academic, vocational, technical, business, professional and home school...and may be grouped in the following manner: universities, colleges offering programs leading to bachelors and graduate degrees, as well as community/junior colleges two-year programs offering programs that lead to associate degrees, diplomas, and professional certificates of completion. At higher education levels, the change is both to how information is accessed and incorporated such as learning management systems (LMS) and network learning resources. In the context of these electronic tools and the digital environment learning builds on a person's literacy skills, and hence the merger between digital (virtual) tools and human reasoning becomes closer to integration of new digital tools, and the challenge is overcoming both a person's ability and epistemic practices. In the modern concept of literacy, literacy is the root of all other technical or digital literacies development.

Transition of Traditional Literacy to Digital Literacy

The evolution of Information Literacy (IL) to now Digital Literacy (DL) has been born out of other literacies indicates the innovation and development of digital technology as an integral component of education, information learning and knowledge. The interconnectedness and transitional development from traditional literacies to IL and now DL can be traced back to the end of the 1960s when the standard definitions of 'literacy' missed out something important from the increasingly visual nature of the media produced by society. John (1969) offered a tentative definition for a concept he called 'visual literacy': 'Visual Literacy refers to a group of vision-competencies a human being can develop by seeing and at the same time having and integrating other sensory experiences. The competency in visual literacy is effective communication and visual media. According to Dankwalba (2021) the transition of literacy can be viewed in chorological order: (1) traditional literacy the set of reading, writing, and numeracy skills. (2) Visual Literacy is the ability to make sense of what you saw, able to create and

comprehend images. (3) Media Literacy ability to create and communicate through various media platforms. (4) Information Literacy is the ability to evaluate and use the necessary information needed for leaning (5) the new literacy known as Digital Literacy is the ability to use IT infrastructures such as computers, mobile phones, and so on for teaching and learning. This is in line with the Allan Martin (2006) analytical order and the comprehensive reviews of the concept of digital literacy and its relation to partly overlapping concepts such as information literacy, library literacy, media literacy and computer literacy. EDUCAUSE (2019) stated that the concept of digital literacy "encompasses a range of skills and knowledge necessary to evaluate, use, and create digital information in various forms. Digital literacies include data literacy, information literacy, visual literacy, media literacy, and metaliteracy." In the modern concept of literacy, traditional literacy is the root of all other technical or digital literacies (Digital Literacy Task Force, 2013).

Furthermore, Mackey and Jacobson (2011) give scholarly definitions of the six foundational literacies that are in agreement with Dankwalba's claims on the transition of literacy which include:

1. **Critical literacy** views readers as participants during reading. Critical literacy focuses on issues of power and promotes reflection, transformation, and action.
2. **Information literacy** is a set of abilities requiring individuals to "recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use the needed information effectively.
3. **Visual literacy** is the ability to understand, interpret, and evaluate visual messages.
4. **Media literacy** is the ability to access, analyze, evaluate, and communicate information in a variety of forms, and is interdisciplinary.
5. **Digital literacy** is the ability to find, evaluate, use, share, and create content using information technologies and the Internet.
6. **Multimodal literacy** is the ability to "interpret the intertextuality of communication events that include

combinations of print, speech, images, sounds, movement, music, and animation,” and the integration of multiple modes of communication and expression.

Digital Literacy and Contemporary Education

Digital literacy has become a topic of discussion in all current educational theories, and most of them recognize the enormous potential of ICTs to personalise teaching and learning processes through making them more adaptive and interactive. UNESCO’s Annual World Report 2009, Information Society Policies (UNESCO, 2009) highlights the major challenge policy makers face: the widening of the digital divide, or the lack of improvement in the area of digital literacy in developing countries. In a growing number of developing countries, digital literacy has become a national priority. Different countries and cultures may have fundamentally different needs for digital literacy. Regular monitoring of school practices often reveals that a good solution in a western country may turn into a dead-end alley when applied in Africa or India. Teacher training is key; however, supplying teachers with “fish” (pre-packaged educational content) but no “net” (digital literacy skills to create locally relevant content) can be useless, even counterproductive. Differences among users’ social backgrounds can represent an equally significant factor.

The hallmark of contemporary education is academic technology (AT) inclusion that incorporates digital literacy, information literacy (IL), and digital information literacy (DIL). Academic technology (AT) is an accumulation of multiple, digital components and formats, whereas technology is a generic term that means a manner of accomplishing a task in a technology process, method, or knowledge (Merriam-Webster, 2015). Flavin (2012) reported that higher-education institutions are investing in digital learning technologies and the virtual learning environments (i.e., academic technology). Ramaley (2014) suggests that these ATs influence higher-education pedagogy. Rockman (2004) found that when digital literacy

is included in general education courses, it represents a strategy for closing the gap across curriculum boundaries because general education courses form the foundation of a common learning experience. Ragains (2006) argues that incorporating digital literacy into subject classes instills in students the ability to think and act creatively, which is required in today’s higher education system.

American Library Association (ALA, 1989) Presidential Committee on Information Literacy report suggests that what previously sufficed as literacy no longer counts as effective knowledge; there is great need for computer, civic, global, and cultural literacies for the United States to compete in the world economy. Kerr (2012) stated that digital literacy has had a profound influence on education, employment, and quality of life especially in contemporary information-driven and information-rich environments. Digital literacy is one of many literacies that appear in the digital educational environment, often described as an overarching literacy. Therefore, digital literacy includes aspects of multi-literacy, as information management, information technology, and information literacy. Many of these areas are indirect components of information-learning skills (Swanson, 2004). The four elements that encompass DL are digital-age literacy, inventive thinking, effective communication, and high productivity. These elements are part of visual, media, computer, network, and information literacies, and Web 2.0. These elements influence higher education and make students learn faster and become lifelong learners.

President Obama declared that October is National information literacy Awareness Month, spurred by the influence digital technology is having on education and information literacy (Obama, 2009). Selwyn (2010) outlines competencies as a range of skills, including (1) the ability to be information literate (i.e., discerning content quality), (2) being adaptively literate (i.e., developing new skills while using information computer technologies (ICT) and recognized universally as technology self-efficacy with AT), and (3) being occupationally literate (i.e., applying these skills in education, business, or domestic environments). The ability to incorporate DL and use AT relies on a variety

of competencies beyond basic computer operations. Ianuzzi (2013) discuss the inconsistencies, where research focuses only generally on digital technology and IL, but must catch up with digital disruptive technologies of Web 2.0 and DIL's impact.

Digital Literacy as a component of Life Skill

Digital literacy skill is beyond IT skills, it also requires critical thinking as Information and communication technologies (ICTs) have penetrated all areas of contemporary life. In this context, digital literacy has become much more than the ability to handle computers – just like traditional literacy and numeracy, it comprises a set of basic skills which include the use and production of digital media, information processing and retrieval, participation in social networks for creation and sharing of knowledge, and a wide range of professional computing skills. Digital literacy improves employability because it is a gate skill, demanded by many employers when they first evaluate a job application. It also works as a catalyst because it enables the acquisition of other important life skills. The origin of the word literacy refers to the ability to read and write. Early descriptions of computer-related literacies also focus on the acquisition of sets of rules and technical capabilities. However, by the end of the 20th century, this definition had expanded considerably. According to the working definition, agreed at the UNESCO June 2003 Expert Meeting in Paris, “literacy is the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, compute and use printed and written materials associated with varying contexts.

Modern life skills encompass an intricate system of knowledge, skills, abilities, and motivational factors that must be developed according to the needs of their specific domains. The populations where digital literacy is most important are ICT users, e-business professionals, and ICT professionals.

ICT user skills are those that should be learnt by all citizens of the knowledge society in order to:

- Select and apply ICT systems and devices effectively;
- utilise common generic software tools in their private lives;
- Use specialised tools for work;
- Flexibly adapt to changes in infrastructure and applications.

E-Business skills are the capabilities needed to exploit business opportunities provided by Internet based applications. These skills are used, among others:

- To rationalise management;
- To promote more efficient and effective performance of organisations;
- To explore new ways of conducting established businesses;
- To establish new businesses.

ICT professionals' skills require high-level, specialized knowledge used for:

- Researching, developing, and designing ICT tools;
- Managing, producing, marketing, and selling tools and services;
- Consulting, integrating, and installing ICT supported applications;
- Maintaining, administrating, supporting, and servicing ICT systems.

Digital Literacy Inclusion Strategies in Higher Education

The most important aspect of contemporary teaching and learning is technological innovation, exploring faculty attitudes toward use of technology in the classroom at university. For both students and teachers to take maximum benefit of the technological innovation in higher education one needs to be digitally literate. Learning builds on a person's literacy skills, and hence the merger between digital (virtual) tools and human reasoning becomes closer to integration of new digital tools, and the challenge is overcoming both a person's ability and epistemic practices. Ianuzzi (2013) suggest that digital literacy and digital information literacy involvement in higher education can successful improve digital competencies in academia and

life. Universities should understand both students' digital competencies and technology perceptions when considering curriculum adjustments to include digital technology. Lea (2013) suggests a provision be made for DL and web literacy, and included as subject-discipline specific. The integration of digital technology advantages with thoughtful modes of practice should be developed and built on established connected learning theory (Gonzalez-Pitino & Estevan-Guitart, 2014). U.S. Department of Education (2006) comment that technology adds value by strengthening academic programs, increasing access, and providing improved models for curriculum development and delivery. Newman, Courturier, and Scurry (2004) argue that both new policies from politicians and expectations handed down from institutional administrators regarding digital literacy because it enhances learning and teaching. Regarding digital literacy inclusion strategies in Higher Education especially Universities, the following factors should be considered:

1. Understanding the implications for university investment in curricula development using academic technology applications.
2. Institutions should provide an environment that fosters DL technology, and educational technology adoption cycle.
3. There should be a consensus across scholarly literature regarding the transience of technology which influences university digital literacy adoption and the uses of academic technology as part of pedagogy.
4. Provision of programs with a purposeful approach to creating DL quality levels with AT in online learning opportunities, and recognizing myriad issues that arise with the transience of technology.
5. The universities should consider the influence on quality, currency, and effectiveness during design of learning experiences that need to be addressed in a relationship with the ways technology changes the learning environment, especially when making recommendations for practices and standards for instructional designers to

work with university in the challenge of DL inclusion in pedagogy.

6. Universities should include digital literacy studies as part of General Studies or to be incorporate as a topic in introduction to computer related courses of study in their institutions.

In addition, Cardwell-Hampton (2008) argues that for institutions to overcome faculty barriers and make changes, implementation of new strategies requires broad, collaborative involvement of all stakeholders when there is absence of conclusive data. The benefits of new, best strategies have a progressive influence, altering the way universities teach and students learn. Another topic regarding DL inclusion is the controversial issue of how effective education technologies are when university personalised subject content learning, thereby tailoring and personalising student learning, and thus enhancing student achievement (Badke, 2012). However, Susan FourtanéJan (2022) reported that Other technologies which will continue to have an impact and see a consistent increase in adoption in the higher education sector include Gamification, Blockchain, Chatbots, and Internet of Things (IoT) as well as Cloud-based technologies for student relationship management (CRM), Learning Management Systems (LMS), and assessment management, among others. She added that a whopping 86 percent of educators are convinced that technology should play a paramount role in how they teach future generations. Indeed, this will resonate on how graduates will be prepared to be in alignment with future jobs.

Thus, the top higher education technology trends to watch out for include Artificial Intelligence (AI), Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Digital Twins, the Metaverse (including digital avatars and NFT art for use in the Metaverse and other Web3-based virtual environments), Internet of Things (IoT), Blockchain, Cloud, Gamification, and Chatbots. These technologies will support the expansion of the Digital Transformation of higher education going forward.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) will play an instrumental role in higher education. AI in education has been projected to reach 3.68 billion

by 2023 and grow over 40 percent overtime to reach \$17.83 billion by 2027. Institutions may expect to reap benefits from using AI for invigilating, grading, and library services, among others. Incorporating AI into the curriculums and supporting its integration will play a paramount role in order to see the benefits from this trend. The University of British Columbia is already using an AI-enabled avatar called Language Chatsim which helps students practice speaking German in a virtual environment.

Virtual and Augmented Reality (VAR): And their combinations of Mixed and Extended Reality (MR/XR) are immersive, experiential technologies with a tremendous capacity for simulations and training in areas such as medicine, engineering, veterinary medicine, and many more. These technologies are central to the Metaverse. They can help the classroom become more interactive and immersive while playing a role engaging learners' senses through comprehensive multisensory experiences, moving forward to the next level: The Internet of Senses (IoS) applied to education.

Digital Twins: A Digital Twin creates a highly complex virtual model which is an exact replica of a physical thing; in this case, we refer to the campus. In 2021, Morehouse College was revealed as a pioneer after creating a Digital Twin of its campus to offer its students a better and more attractive solution for remote learning, a solution that offers a superior experience than Zoom.

The Metaverse: The Metaversity promises to provide an entire virtual world where students and faculty can interact remotely, efficiently, engaging in educational and interactive worlds.

Internet of Things (IoT): The success and expansion of an all-connected campus depends on the network. A 5G, real-time network empowers the connected campus bringing accessibility only to students, administrators, and faculty but also to all the connected things and equipment which are part of it. The IoT goes hand-in-hand with a smart automated campus.

Blockchain technology provides secure storage for students' records and other records.

Blockchain will remain an edtech trend in 2023. It is expected to grow 85.9 percent from 2022 throughout 2030.

Cloud Computing in the form of cloud-based services will continue to expand during 2023. Cloud-based infrastructure will allow limitless virtual libraries to assist students and academics in their research. With the help of the Cloud, online education platforms can handle vast amounts of video content, 3D-modeling and more, making it easy for students to share their work with their teachers as well as accessing limitless video lectures.

Gamification: Although not new, game-based learning will continue to grow in 2023. Tedious and complex classes can become enjoyable and thus increase student engagement.

Chatbots are autonomous agents which use various Artificial Intelligence techniques such as Natural Learning Processing (NLP), Automatic Speech Recognition, Data Mining, Machine Learning, and Sentiment Analysis. In higher education, chatbots can drive student engagement. They can answer queries such as lesson plans, student modules, assignments, and deadlines. They improve student retention; play a role in admission, career services, and mental health support. In the future, pedagogical chatbots are going to be incorporated into the classroom. The aim of pedagogical chatbots (conversational agents) is to improve students' engagement, according to research conducted by the University of Granada, Spain. Chatbots in higher education are a trend to keep an eye on in 2023.

Conclusion

Digital literacy has become a widely studied topic for connecting people, participation in education, government and public affairs. As a result, universities should encourage the management, academia and faculty members to train students and effectively acquire, preserve and disseminate knowledge on the importance of digital literacy in achieving success and improving students' academic performance. Digital Literacy (DL) has been born out of other literacies such as traditional literacy, visual literacy, media literacy

and information literacy which indicate the transition and development of the modern literacy (digital literacy) from the traditional literacy (conventional) and with a combination of academic technology as an integral component of education, information learning and knowledge it become the hallmark of education in the 21st century.

Recommendations

1. Digital literacy workshops, seminars, symposia and service orientation should be organized in Universities in Nigeria.
2. University should start digital literacy programs with appropriate funds to provide a sound technical background for both staff and students
3. Universities should integrate digital literacy as a course module in general studies courses.

References

Allen Martin & Grudziecki, J. (2006). DigEuLit: Concepts and tools for digital literacy development. *Innovation in teaching and learning in information and computer sciences*, 5(4), 249-267.

American Library Association (1989). Presidential committee on information literacy: Final report. Chicago: American Libraries Association. Retrieved from <http://ala.org/acrl/publications/whitepapers/presidential>

Badke, W. B. (2012). *Teaching research process: The faculty development of skilled student researchers*. Oxford, UK: Chandos Information Professional Series

Cardwell-Hampton, N. (2008). Faculty perceptions about technology in eight community colleges in the Tennessee Board of Regents higher education system (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). East Tennessee State University, Nashville, Tennessee.

Christensen, C. M., & Eyring, H. J. (2011). *The innovative university: Changing the DNA of*

higher education from the inside out. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.

Christiaan Henny (2016) digital-literacy-contemporary-education-christiaan henny linkin

Dankwalba I.A. (2021). Utilisation of Digital Literacy for Electronic Information Search in Private University in Abuja. Masters Dissertation.

Digital Literacy Taskforce (2013). Digital literacy, libraries, and public policy. Retrieved from <http://www.ala.org/news/press-releases/2013/06/ala-task-force-releases-digital-literacy-recommendations>.

EDUCAUSE Learning Initiative (2019). Things-you-should-know-about-digital-literacies. <https://library.educause.edu/resources/2019/7/7->

Flavin, M. (2012). Disruptive technologies in higher education. *Research in Learning Technology*, 20, 1–7. Retrieved from <http://www.researchinlearningtechnology.net/index.php/rlt/article/view/19184>.

Gonzalez-Patino, J., & Esteban-Guitart, M. (2014). Some of the challenges and experiences of formal education in a mobile centric society (MCS). *Digital Education Review*, 25, 64–85.

John Debes. (1969). The loom of visual literacy: An overview. *Audiovisual Instruction*, 14, 25–27

Ianuzzi, P.A. (2013). Info Lit 2.0 or Déjà vu? *Communications in Information Literacy*, 7(2), 98–107.

Kerr, P. (2012). Explicit goals, implicit outcomes: Information literacy education in developing university graduate attributes. *UWI Quality Education Forum*, 18(January), 71–88.

Lea, M. R. (2013). Reclaiming literacies: competing textual practices in a digital higher education. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 18(1), 106–118.

Mackey, T. P., & Jacobson, T. (2011). Reframing information literacy as a metaliteracy. *College & Research Libraries*, 76(1), 62–78. Retrieved from <http://crl.acrl.org/content/72/1/62.full.pdf>

- Merriam-Webster (2015). Merriam-Webster: Dictionary and thesaurus, online dictionary. An Encyclopedia Britannica Company: Merriam-Webster, Incorporated. Retrieved from <http://www.merriam-webster.com/>
- National Center for Education Statistics (2000), Teachers Tools for The 21st Century: A Report on Teacher's Use of Technology, Education Public Center (ED Pubs), Jessup, MD.
- Newman, F., Couturier, L., & Scurry, J. (2004). *The future of higher education: Rhetoric, reality, and the risks of the market*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Obama, B. (2009). National information literacy awareness month, 2009. The President of the United States of America: A Proclamation. Retrieved from http://www.whitehouse.gov/assets/documents/2009literacy_prc_rel.pdf
- Oblinger, D. and Oblinger, J.L. (2005), Educating the Net Generation, EDUCAUSE, Boulder, CO.
- Ragains, P. (2006). *Information literacy instruction that works: A guide to teaching by discipline and student population*. New York, NY: Neal-Schman.
- Ramaley, J. A. (2014). The changing role of higher education: Learning to deal with wicked problems. *Journal of Higher Education Outreach and Engagement*, 18(3), 7–22. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unomaha.edu/slcehighered/167>
- Roberts, S., & Hunter, D. (2011). New library, new librarian, new student: Using LibGuides to reach the virtual student. *Journal of Library & Information Services in Distance Learning*, 5(1/2), 67–75.
- Schwitzer, A. M., Ancis, J. R., & Brown, N. (2001). Promoting student learning and student development at a distance: Student affairs concepts and practices for televised instruction and other forms of distance learning. Lanham, MD: American College Personnel Association.
- Schraw, G. (2013). Conceptual integration and measurement of epistemological and ontological beliefs in educational research. *ISRN Education*, 2013, 1-19. Retrieved from <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/isrn/2013/327680/cta/>
- Selwyn, N. (2010). Degrees of digital division: Reconsidering digital inequalities and contemporary higher education. In *Redefining the digital divide in higher education* [online monograph]. *Revista de Universidad y Sociedad del Conocimiento (RUSC)*. 7(1), UOC. [Accessed 11/11/2015]. Retrieved from http://rusc.uoc.edu/ojs/index.php/rusc/article/view/v7n1_selwyn.
- Säljö, R. (2012). Literacy, digital literacy and epistemic practices: The co-evolution of hybrid minds and external memory systems. *Nordic Journal of Digital Literacy*, 7(01), 5-19.
- Susan FourtanéJan (2022). future-higher-education-chatbots-improved-student-retention <https://www.fierceeducation.com/leadership/>
- Swanson, T. A. (2004). A radical step: Implementing a critical information literacy model. *Portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 4(2), 259–273.
- UNESCO (2021). Literacy. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/literacy>
- UNESCO (2004). The Plurality of Literacy and its Implications for Policies. UNESCO Education Sector Position Paper. (p. 13)<http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0013/001362/136246e.pdf>
- UNESCO (2009). Information Society Policies. Annual world report.http://portal.unesco.org/ci/en/files/29547/12668551003ifap_world_report_2009.pdf
- Venezky, R. and Kárpáti A. (Eds., 2004): ICT, Education and Innovation. Special Issue, Education, Communication and Information. Vol. 4, No. 1.
- U.S. Department of Education (2006). A test of leadership, charting the future of U.S.

- higher education. Spellings
Commission Report. Jessup, MD:
Education Publication center.
Retrieved from
[https://www2.ed.gov/about/bdscomm/lis
t/hiedfuture/reports/finalreport. pdf](https://www2.ed.gov/about/bdscomm/list/hiedfuture/reports/finalreport.pdf)
- Wesch, M. (2011). *The old revolution. 21st
century: Viewpoint*. Campus Technology.
Retrieved
from
[https://campustechnology.com/Articles/2
011/03/23/The-Old-Revolution.aspx?p=1](https://campustechnology.com/Articles/2011/03/23/The-Old-Revolution.aspx?p=1)
- Wesch, M. (2008). *A vision of students today (and
what teachers must do)*. Encyclopedia
Britannica [blog]. Retrievedv from
<http://www.britannica.com/blogs/2008/1>

0/a-vision- of-students-today-
whateachers-must-do/